

Study on Customer Segmentation Based on Clustering Algorithms using Machine Learning

Ms. Sonu Maria Antony
PG Scholar

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
sonumariaantony@mca.ajce.in

Mr. T J Jobin

Assistant Professor
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
tjjobin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— The technique of segmenting clients based on examples of their past purchasing behavior is known as customer segmentation. Predictions are made using information from mall customers. Information on mall customers is comprised of unlabeled data. Using different clustering algorithms, the goal is to put consumers into groups based on their annual income and spending score.

Keywords—Customer Segmentation, K-Means, DBSCAN, Mean Shift, Agglomerative

I. INTRODUCTION

As more and more new companies emerge on a regular basis, it is crucial for existing companies to implement marketing strategies in order to remain competitive. "Change or perish" is the basic marketing tenet in the modern world. As the number of consumers increases, it becomes increasingly challenging for businesses to meet each customer's needs. In this case, data mining can be used to find hidden trends in a company's database. An effective way for businesses to manage a huge client base is through the use of customer segmentation, a data mining technique. Because segmentation opens up so many new research opportunities, the marketing strategy may be impacted directly or indirectly. For instance, segmentation can show how to tailor marketing techniques for each section, how to give discounts to a certain segment, and how to comprehend the customer-object relationship, which the organization had not previously understood. By using customer segmentation to comprehend what their clients are buying, businesses may provide better services to their customers and boost customer happiness. Additionally, it enables companies to pinpoint their target customers and improve their marketing strategies to increase sales from them.

Because the business world is so cutthroat, businesses must cater to the needs of their existing clients and draw in new ones based on their desires in order to expand and increase sales. Each consumer has different demands, and it takes time and effort to determine what those needs are. This results from the reality that customers have various requirements, standards, and preferences. Consumer segmentation divides customers into category based on comparable characteristics, in opposition to a "one-size-fits-all" approach. Depending on the customers, customer segmentation is a marketing strategy that separates the market into homogeneous groups. Customers are divided into groups depending on a variety of characteristics, including information on geographic conditions, economic conditions, demographic conditions, and beh

avioural patterns. This process is known as customer segmentation. A customer segmentation plan can help a company spend its marketing budget more effectively, gain an advantage over competitors, and show that it has a better understanding of customer expectation. Additionally, it can assist a company in strengthening its brand strategy, finding new market opportunities, evaluating client retention, and improving marketing efficiency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A comprehensive model based on generalized association rules and decision tree technology was put out by Haiying Ma [1]. The model is utilized by an online store to categorize its customers. It can assist in decision-making and enable e-commerce businesses better understand their customers so they can offer more specialized services to their clients.

Nikhil Patankar, Soham Dixit, Akshay Bhamare, Ashutosh Darpel and Ritik Raina [2] used K-means clustering algorithm based on behavioral characteristics customers are classified.

An overview of a particular hierarchical clustering algorithm is provided by Marjan Kuchakist [3]. After classifying clustering techniques, the author turned his attention primarily to hierarchical clustering algorithms. The description of these techniques included a focus on minimizing disc I/O operations, which in turn reduced time complexity. Additionally, they listed the characteristics, benefits, and drawbacks of each algorithm under consideration. In the end, each one was compared based on how they were alike and different.

P. Anitha [4] used the k-means method to analyze the RFM model and evaluate consumer purchasing patterns across various locations.

BIRCH (Balanced Iterative Reducing and Clustering utilising Hierarchies), a method Tian Zhang [5] designed and validated, is an agglomerative hierarchical clustering technique that is especially suited for huge databases. After constructing the highest quality clusters possible with the resources at hand, BIRCH dynamically and progressively clusters incoming multidimensional metric data points. With just one scan of the data, BIRCH typically creates a nice cluster, and a few further scans can improve the quality even more. BIRCH was also the first clustering technique in the database field to be suggested that can properly handle noise. Through

a number of studies, the author assesses BIRCH's space/time efficiency, data input order sensitivity, and cluster quality.

III. SEGMENTATION TYPES

A. Behavioral Segmentation

Behavioral segmentation is the most used and efficient segmentation methods because it is easy to be collecting data. The segmenting is done on the basis of the customer's behavior. The behavioral pattern can be identified through the buying pattern, usage, engagement level, the quality, quantity and brand of the product etc. This will help the companies to identify the behavior of the customers and they will be able to provide the products according to this data.

B. Demographic Segmentation

Demographic segmentation is the segmentation based on life stage information or socio-demographic information such as age, gender, education, occupation, marital status, income etc. because it is easy to be collecting data. The segmenting is done on the basis of the customer's behavior. This segmentation helps to focus more on products for each life stage.

C. Geographic Segmentation

Geographic segmentation is the segmentation based on areas such as country, states, urban, rural, coastal etc. This will help the company to focus on the customers more in the region with fewer sales and also helps to identify the priority of orders in each region.

D. Psychographic Segmentation

Psychographic segmentation is the segmentation based on the customer lifestyle, beliefs, opinion, activities, interest, jobs etc. This will help the company to identify the customer needs according to their lifestyle, attitude, jobs etc.

E. Propensity Based Segmentation

Propensity based segmentation is the segmentation based on some scores such as churn scores, propensity scores etc. This segmentation contains computation and the binning of customers into groups according to the score.

IV. CLUSTERING TECHNIQUES

A. K-Means Clustering

K-Means Clustering is an example of Exclusive Clustering and belongs to the category of Unsupervised Machine Learning Algorithm. The number of specified clusters, or "K," in the K-Means algorithm. In this centroid-based method, each cluster is connected to a centroid. Reducing the overall distances between the data points and the clusters they are a part of is the main objective of this technique.

B. Density-Based Clustering

Density-Based Clustering also known as DBSCAN is based upon the notion of clusters and noise which is used to get a

cluster of arbitrary shapes. It is used to differentiate the high-density cluster from the low-density cluster. It is efficient for large data set. The main concept of the DBSCAN is core samples, or samples that are in high-density areas. eps and min samples are two parameters. eps is the neighbourhood of a point, x , or radius of a circle (or hypersphere in N-D space) with x as centre. minPts is the minimum number of points in neighbourhood to form a dense region. Higher min_samples or lower eps imply a cluster requires a higher density to develop.

C. MeanShift Clustering

Mean Shift is an unsupervised clustering algorithm also known as the Mode-seeking algorithm that aims to discover blobs in a smooth density of samples. It is a centroid-based technique that operates by revising potential centroids to be the average of the points inside a specified region (also called bandwidth). To create the final collection of centroids, these candidates are then filtered in a post-processing stage to get rid of near-duplicates. As a result, unlike KMeans, we don't need to select the number of clusters. assigns the data points to the clusters iteratively by shifting points towards the mode (mode is the highest density of data points in the region, in the context of the MeanShift).

D. Agglomerative Clustering

Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering is a bottom-up clustering method in which sub-clusters of clusters contain sub-clusters of their own, and so on. These atomic clusters are then connected to build higher and higher clusters until all the objects are in that single cluster, or until a clear termination condition is required, after finding each object in the cluster. This kind makes use of several hierarchical clustering methods. The only difference between them is in how they define cluster similarity.

V. METHODOLOGY

The tool used for the implementation part is Jupyter Notebook which is an open-source, web-based interactive environment that lets you create and share documents with real-time code, mathematical equations, visuals, maps, charts, and textual narratives.

1. Dataset

In this instance, the Mall Customers are being utilized. Information on mall customers, including their annual income, genre, age, and spending score, is included in the unlabeled data. Our goal is to categorize consumers based on important factors including annual income and spending score. The dataset is:

CustomerID	Gender	Age	Annual Income (k\$)	Spending Score (1-100)
0	1 Male	19	15	39
1	2 Male	21	15	81
2	3 Female	20	16	6
3	4 Female	23	16	77
4	5 Female	31	17	40

Fig 1. Dataset

2. K-Means Clustering

A. Elbow Method

The "elbow" approach of deciding on the ideal number of clusters for K-means clustering is implemented by the K-Elbow Visualizer. A straightforward unsupervised machine learning algorithm called K-means divides data into a predetermined number (k) of clusters. The technique is relatively naive in that it assigns all members to k clusters even when that k is not appropriate for the dataset because the user must indicate in advance which k to choose. The elbow technique applies k-means clustering to the dataset using a range of k values (for example, 1-10), and computes the average score for each value of k. The distortion score, which is calculated by default, is the sum of the square distances between each point and its designated centre.

In order to find an appropriate number of clusters, the elbow method will be used. In this method for this case, the inertia for a number of clusters between 2 and 10 will be calculated. The rule is to choose the number of clusters where you see a kink or "an elbow" in the graph.

The graph below shows the inertia for selected range of clusters.

Fig 2. Elbow Method

No apparent "elbow" can be seen. It seems fair to offer a choice of five or six clusters. Let's see the silhouette score.

B. Silhouette Score Method

The resulting clusters' separation distance can be examined using silhouette analysis. By showing a measure of how close each point in one cluster is to points in the neighboring clusters, the silhouette plot provides a visual method to assess characteristics like the number of clusters. This metric's range is [-1, 1].

The sample is distant from the surrounding clusters if the silhouette coefficients (as these values are known) are close to +1. Indicated by a value of 0, a sample is on or very near the boundary between two neighboring clusters, while negative values suggest that the sample may have been mistakenly assigned to another cluster.

Fig 3. Silhouette Score Method

The best possibilities, according to the silhouette score technique, are 6 or 5 clusters, respectively. Let's compare both.

K-Means algorithm generated the following 5 clusters:

Fig 4. K-Means with 5 clusters

- 0 - Customers with high annual income and high spending score
- 1 - Customers with medium annual income and medium spending score
- 2 - Customers with low annual income and high spending score
- 3 - Customers with high annual income and low spending score
- 4 - Customers with low annual income and low spending score

Sizes of the clusters:

Cluster	KM5_size
0	79
1	36
2	23
3	23
4	39

Fig 5. Size of clusters in K-Means with 5 clusters

The biggest cluster is a cluster number 1 with 80 observations ("medium-medium" clients). There are two the smallest ones

each containing 23 observations (cluster 3 “high-high” and cluster 0 “low-high” clients).

K-Means algorithm generated the following 6 clusters:

Fig 6. K-Means with 6 clusters

- 0 - Customers with medium annual income and medium spending score
- 1 - Customers with high annual income and high spending score
- 2 - Customers with medium annual income and medium spending score
- 3 - Customers with low annual income and low spending score
- 4 - Customers with high annual income and low spending score
- 5 - Customers with low annual income and high spending score

Sizes of the clusters:

KM6_size	
Cluster	Size
0	35
1	45
2	39
3	22
4	21
5	38

Fig 7. Size of clusters in K-Means with 6 clusters

3. DBSCAN

Fig 8. DBSCAN with 5 clusters

The above graph demonstrates that some points are outliers; these points do not satisfy the distance and sample size requirements to be classified as a cluster.

Sizes of the clusters:

DBSCAN_sizes	
Cluster	Size
-1	18
0	112
1	8
2	34
3	24
4	4

Fig 9. Size of clusters in DBSCAN with 5 clusters

DBSCAN created 5 clusters plus outliers (-1). Clusters 0–4 range greatly in size; some have only 4–8 observations. 18 outliers are present.

4. MeanShift

MeanShift algorithm generated the following 5 clusters:

Fig 10. MeanShift with 5 clusters

Sizes of the clusters:

Cluster	MS_size
0	80
1	39
2	36
3	22
4	23

Fig 11. Size of clusters in MeanShift with 5 clusters

5. Agglomerative Clustering

Agglomerative Clustering algorithm generated the following 5 clusters:

Fig 12. Agglomerative with 5 clusters

Sizes of the clusters:

Cluster	Agg_size
0	35
1	83
2	39
3	20
4	23

Fig 13. Size of clusters in Agglomerative with 5 clusters

VI. RESULT

This result shows that the given dataset can be classified into various clusters. Four algorithms were used they are KMeans clustering, DBSCAN, MeanShift and Agglomerative clustering. The size of clusters formed by applying each clustering algorithms are shown below:

Cluster	KM5_size	KM6_size	DBSCAN_sizes	MS_size	Agg_size
-1	NaN	NaN	18.0	NaN	NaN
0	23.0	38.0	112.0	80.0	35.0
1	36.0	45.0	8.0	39.0	83.0
2	79.0	39.0	34.0	36.0	39.0
3	23.0	35.0	24.0	22.0	20.0
4	39.0	22.0	4.0	23.0	23.0
5	NaN	21.0	NaN	NaN	NaN

Fig 14. Size of clusters for each algorithm

VII. CONCLUSION

KMeans with six clusters appear to have more uniformly distributed observations. DBSCAN, on the other hand, performed poorly since it was unable to correctly recognize clusters of different densities despite being able to identify outliers in all cases (which are present in this case). The magnitude of the data is another factor that could be causing DBSCAN to perform poorly; DBSCAN is known to function well when the size of the data is huge. K-means performance with 5 clusters. The algorithms of MeanShift and Agglomerative were essentially identical.

In order to more precisely identify and categorise clients based on their purchasing patterns, income level, age, and other criteria, segmentation can benefit the majority of organizations. A method for segmenting or subdividing photos according to color scheme, amount of grey, contract, and other factors called clustering. For upselling and cross-selling in industries like ecommerce, understanding consumer segmentation is crucial. But this is only the very beginning in terms of customer mall spending. Segmenting customers or buyers is a big concept in and of itself.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Haiying Ma, "A Study on Customer Segmentation for E-Commerce Using the Generalized Association Rules and Decision Tree," American Journal of Industrial and Business Management, vol. 5, pp. 813-818, 2015. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/ajibm.2015.512078>.
- [2] Prof. Nikhil Patankar, Soham Dixit, Akshay Bhamare, Ashutosh Darpel and Ritik Raina. Customer Segmentation Using Machine Learning. doi:10.3233/APC210200
- [3] MarjanKuchaki Rafsanjani, Zahra Asghari Varzaneh, Nasibeh Emami Chukanlo (2012), A survey of hierarchical clustering algorithms, The Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science, 5,,3, pp.229- 240.
- [4] P. Anitha, Malini M. Patil. RFM model for customer purchase behavior using K-Means algorithm[J]. Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences, 2019.
- [5] Tian Zhang, Raghu Ramakrishnan, MironLinvy (1996), BIRCH: an efficient data clustering method for large databases, International Conference on Management of Data, In Proc. of 1996 ACM-SIGMOD Montreal. Quebec.
- [6] www.kaggle.com/datasets/sonalisingh1411/mallcustomersdataset